

Solvent Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Rhenium(VII) using Mixed Ligands

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A new method is proposed for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of rhenium(VII) using 2-mercaptobenzo- γ -thiopyrone (MBTP) and ammonium thiocyanate as mixed ligands. The colour formation is complete in 30 min. and the complex is stable for over 24 hr at room temperature. The complex is formed in 1.8-2.6 *N* HCl medium and is extracted into acetophenone, giving an absorbance maximum at 435 nm. The method is more sensitive than any of the other spectrophotometric methods reported for rhenium. Many commonly associated ions do not interfere; while serious interferences from Mo⁶⁺, W⁶⁺, U⁶⁺, V⁵⁺, Se⁴⁺, Ni²⁺, and Cu²⁺ are eliminated by a chloroform-tertiary amine extraction prior to the determination of rhenium. An improved method for the separation of molybdenum(VI) before the determination of rhenium is also developed. Three substituted derivatives of MBTP have also been tried as mixed ligands with ammonium thiocyanate.

In a previous communication¹ we have shown that the sensitivity of the colour reaction for the solvent extraction and spectrophotometric determination of rhenium with thiocyanate in presence of stannous chloride can be considerably increased if a mixture of thiocyanate and thiourea are used. In the present work we have observed that the sensitivity of the rhenium reaction can be further increased if a mixture of thiocyanate and potassium salt of 2-mercaptobenzo- γ -thiopyrone, MBTP, (i) are used as mixed ligands.

2-mercaptobenzo- γ -thiopyrone (i)

Based on this colour reaction, an efficient and sensitive spectrophotometric method is developed which is described in this paper.

5-hydroxy-8-nitro(ii), 7-hydroxy-8-nitro-(iii) and 5-hydroxy-6, 8-dinitro(iv) derivatives of MBTP were also prepared and employed as mixed ligands with thiocyanate to find out their applicability.

Experimental

The reagent MBTP was prepared by refluxing acetophenone, carbon disulphide and alcoholic potassium hydroxide³; the derivatives of MBTP were prepared in a similar way using 3-nitro-6-hydroxy acetophenone⁴, 3-nitro-4-hydroxy acetophenone⁵ and 3, 5-dinitro-6-hydroxy acetophenone⁶ in place of acetophenone. The solid obtained in each case was filtered and washed with

ether. Recrystallisation from a 1:1 chloroform-ether mixture gave pale yellow crystals for MBTP and yellow, yellowish green and yellowish brown crystals for the derivatives respectively. Analysis: (i) Found 27.52% S and 16.80% K; calcd. for C₉H₅OS₂K, 27.57% S and 16.5% K. (ii) Found 21.80% S, 13.42% K and 4.84% N; calcd. for C₉H₄O₄NS₂K, 21.84% S, 13.35% K and 4.78% N. (iii) Found 21.92% S, 13.40% K and 4.85% N; calcd. for C₉H₄O₄NS₂K, 21.84% S, 13.35% K and 4.78% N. (iv) Found 18.85% S, 11.62% K and 8.32% N; calcd. for C₉H₃O₆N₂S₂K, 18.93% S, 11.57% K and 8.28% N.

Aqueous solution of 5% (W/V) ammonium thiocyanate and 1% (W/V) MBTP were used as mixed ligands reagent.

Stannous chloride solution was prepared by dissolving 11.5 g SnCl₂ · 2H₂O in 17 ml conc. HCl with dilution to 100 ml with distilled water.

Potassium perrhenate was obtained from Johnson Matthey and Co. Ltd., London, and was used without further purification. A standard solution of rhenium was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of potassium perrhenate in distilled water and making up the volume to 100 ml. The rhenium content per ml was determined spectrophotometrically using thiocyanate-stannous chloride method².

Acetophenone (BDH) used for extraction was purified by distillation.

All other reagents used were of AnalaR quality.

Apparatus

Absorbances were measured with a Beckmann DU2 spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cells.

Procedure

Place an aliquot of the rhenium solution containing 3 to 40 μg of the metal in a separatory funnel and add 1 ml of 10 M HCl followed by 2 ml of 5% (W/V) ammonium thiocyanate, 1 ml of 1% (W/V) MBTP and 1 ml of stannous chloride solution. Shake gently for 1 min. and set aside for 30 min. for colour to develop. Then extract the colour with 3 ml of acetophenone and draw out the solvent layer into a small beaker containing 1 g anhydrous sodium sulphate. Repeat the extraction twice more with 2 ml portions of acetophenone and collect in the same beaker. Transfer the combined extract to a 10 ml volumetric flask and make up the volume with the solvent. Measure the absorbance at 435 nm against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The absorbance spectra of rhenium thiocyanate, rhenium-MBTP and the mixed ligand complexes are shown in Fig 1. The absorbance of the mixed ligand complex increases from 375 nm, passes through a maximum at 435 nm and then decreases, whereas the absorbance of the reagent blank decreases from 375 nm upto 440 nm and then slightly increases. For spectrophotometric measurements 435 nm was chosen as the optimum wavelength.

Maximum colour intensity was obtained in 1.8 to 2.6 N hydrochloric acid. Sulphuric acid and nitric acid were found unsuitable, because the former produced a turbidity while the latter reduced the colour intensity.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra

- a) Reagent (1 ml 10 M HCl, 2 ml 5% (W/V) ammonium thiocyanate, 1 ml 1% (W/V) MBTP and 1 ml stannous chloride) vs. acetophenone blank.
- b) 1.43 ppm rhenium + reagent vs. acetophenone blank.
- c) 1.43 ppm rhenium + reagent vs. reagent blank.
- d) 1.43 ppm rhenium + reagent (without ammonium thiocyanate) vs. acetophenone blank.

Absorbance remained constant from 1.7 to 3.1 ml of 5% (W/V) ammonium thiocyanate, 0.9 to 2.5 ml of 1% (W/V) MBTP and 0.9 to 1.4 ml of stannous chloride. However, 2 ml of thiocyanate, 1 ml of stannous chloride were used for experimental purposes.

The order of addition of ligands to rhenium solution containing hydrochloric acid had no effect on absorbance, but stannous chloride should be added only at the end.

Variation of temperature between 150° and 50° had no effect on colour formation. The complex was stable for over 24 hr at room temperature.

Optimum range, sensitivity and photometric error

The colour system obeyed Beer's law from 0.3 to 4.2 ppm of rhenium at 435 nm and the optimum concentration range determined by the method of Ringbom⁷ was 0.5 to 3 ppm. In this range the percentage relative analytical error per 1% absolute photometric error⁸ was 2.9. The photometric sensitivity of the method was 0.003 $\mu\text{g Re}/\text{Cm}^2$ at 435 nm.

The absorbance spectra of mixed ligand complexes of rhenium with thiocyanate and the three derivatives of MBTP are shown in Fig 2 with those of the respective

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra

(A', B', C') Reagent, 1 ml 10 M HCl, 2 ml 5% (W/V) ammonium thiocyanate, 1 ml 1% (W/V) substituted derivative of MBTP (5-hydroxy-8-nitro MBTP, 7-hydroxy-8-nitro MBTP and 5-hydroxy-6, 8-dinitro MBTP respectively) 1 ml stannous chloride vs. acetophenone blank.

(A, B, C) 2.86 ppm rhenium + reagent as above vs. acetophenone blank.

reagent blanks. The sensitivities of colour reactions in these cases were lower than that of rhenium-thiocyanate complex. Hence, these are not recommended for spectrophotometric determination of rhenium.

Interferences

The following ions were tolerated upto the amounts shown in brackets: As³⁺ and Sb³⁺ (50 folds); Cd²⁺, Hg²⁺ and Bi³⁺ (100 folds); Ce⁴⁺ (500 folds); Mn²⁺, Fe²⁺, phosphate and borate (1000 folds); Na⁺, K⁺, Be²⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺, Zn²⁺, Pb²⁺, Al³⁺, La³⁺, Ti⁴⁺, Zr⁴⁺, oxalate, chloride, citrate, tartrate and acetate (2000 folds). However, serious interferences were observed for Mo⁶⁺, W⁶⁺, U⁶⁺, V⁵⁺, Se⁴⁺, Fe³⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ag⁺ and Tl⁺; but the interference from Mo⁶⁺, U⁶⁺, V⁵⁺, Se⁴⁺, Ni²⁺ and Cu²⁺ can be eliminated by a tertiary amine-chloroform extraction¹⁰ prior to the determination of rhenium. It was also found that the interference of Mo⁶⁺ can be avoided by extracting it as the pink molybdenum-MBTP complex into a 1 : 1 mixture of carbon tetrachloride and benzene, the procedure of which is mentioned below:

To a mixture containing 12.5 ppm of Re⁷⁺ and a known amount of Mo⁶⁺ in a separatory funnel, add 2 ml of 10 M HCl, followed by a slight excess of 1% (W/V) MBTP (approximately 0.05 g MBTP required for 25 µg of Mo⁶⁺), shake well for 2 min. and let stand for about 5 min. for the pink colour to develop. Then add about 5 ml of the solvent mixture, shake well, allow layers to separate, drain the bottom solvent mixture layer and discard. If the aqueous layer has pink colour, repeat the extraction once more. Add a fresh quantity of reagent solution and test for completion of reaction. If pink colour is developed repeat the operations until further addition of reagent solution no longer produces a pink colour. The solvent mixture extracts excess of reagent also and the aqueous solution will be colourless after removal of molybdenum. Finally adjust the acidity of the aqueous medium to be 1.8–2.6 N and determine rhenium by the proposed method. The results are summarised in Table 1. The reagent MBTP behaves similarly to sodium ethyl xanthate⁹ in separating molybdenum from solutions containing rhenium.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF RHENIUM AFTER SEPARATION OF MOLYBDENUM BY THE PROPOSED EXTRACTION METHOD.

No.	Mo present ppm	Re taken ppm	Re found ppm
I	23.6	12.50	12.45
II	47.2	12.50	12.47
III	118.0	12.50	12.50
IV	36.0	12.50	12.45
V	1180.0	12.50	12.52
VI	2360.0	12.50	12.47

Applications

The proposed method was used for the determination of rhenium in synthetic mixtures, the composition and results of which are given in Table 2. The interferences from Mo⁶⁺, W⁶⁺ and V⁵⁺ in the mixtures were eliminated by extraction with a solution of tertiary amine in chloroform.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF RHENIUM IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

No.	Composition of mixtures	Re(VII) ppm added	Re(VII) ppm found*
I.	Mo ⁶⁺ (20), W ⁶⁺ (5), U ⁶⁺ (5), V ⁵⁺ (5), Si ⁴⁺ (5), Bi ³⁺ (5)	12.50	12.44
II.	Mo ⁶⁺ (40), W ⁶⁺ (10), U ⁶⁺ (10), V ⁵⁺ (10), Si ⁴⁺ (10), Bi ³⁺ (5)	12.50	12.40
III.	Mo ⁶⁺ (60), W ⁶⁺ (20), U ⁶⁺ (20), V ⁵⁺ (20), Si ⁴⁺ (20), Bi ³⁺ (5)	12.50	12.42

Numbers in brackets indicate the amount of metal in mg.

* average of two experiments.

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